

SYNOPSIS REPORT

**Design and Development of an Amphibian Ambulance
for Riverine Areas**

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the Degree of

Doctor of Philosophy

By

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1. Abstract

Despite rapid urbanisation, majority of the population of Assam inhabit the remote rural areas, and out of this population, 2.5 million people live in the riverine island (popularly known as char- chapari areas in local language). Many places in riverine areas in Assam are totally inaccessible by road in spite of expanding rural road networks under Pradhan Mantri Gram Swarak Yojana (PMGSY). These riverine islands and many other areas are affected by floods created by the river Brahmaputra and its tributaries in monsoons. As a result, the health services for the people living in these areas are badly affected. To provide health care facilities to the riverine areas, the C-NES (Centre for North East Studies and Policy Research) first developed innovative ideas for implementation to reach the poor and marginalized group by introducing boat based health services called boat clinics. Later, when Government of India introduced NRHM (National Rural Health Mission) to make health services available to the rural population, Government of Assam based on success of boat clinic operated by C-NES, collaborated with it through expansion of boat clinic to make health services available to riverine rural communities in Assam. Although the government expanded boat clinics to cover bigger area, people found it difficult to access these in emergencies, since patients cannot be easily transported by road to these boat clinics in absence of proper road. To bridge this gap requires appropriate ambulances. An attempt was made to understand the existing scenario of health services in different parts of the country and also globally in under-privileged/ under-developed areas regarding transportation of patients and rural ambulance service. It was found that, in most of the developing countries people need to travel to health care centres by walking or by taking whatever mode of transport is available including buses, rural taxis, private cars, bicycles, animal-drawn carts and local stretchers (Starkey, 2005). To facilitate access to medical services, local communities and transport service providers can work together to plan an appropriate and sustainable transporting technology/system. 'eRanger Production' company designed motorbike ambulance for emergency medical services for obstetric care at the district hospital of Masselleh region, Kambia which provided an innovative, cost effective solution to the problem of emergency medical transport in remote areas (www.eranger.com, 25 May'2011). The present reality is that motorcycles increasingly provide affordable rural transport services. However, this type of transportation is a complicated one for use in riverine areas. Three Canadian students made a stretcher of bamboo called the bambulance stretcher and trailer frame composed of 2-inch diameter

bamboo poles, connected with uniform triangular gusset joints. Every day in Africa and the developing world, thousands of people are suffering from HIV/ AIDS, malaria and other serious illness because they have no access to emergency and general health care services (Boruah, 2011).

The purpose of this research is to facilitate a solution to provide transport to and from local health centres. Ability to safely and comfortably carry one patient and an outreach medical worker, and emergency supplies for on-site treatment, it can greatly reduce the time taken to get essential and urgent medical assistance to remote communities. To accomplish the stated purpose; a combination of research methods featuring literature survey, questionnaire, direct observation, one to one interview for data collection; statistical analysis of the gathered data, work study technique, prototype development and testing has been used.

After gathering necessary information, it was felt that, for remote riverine areas of Assam, to provide access to rural health care facilities with existing economic situation, road condition and environmental phenomenon, there is a need to design an amphibian ambulance.

The prototype of the proposed amphibian ambulance has been designed and developed as a part of doctoral research in the Department of Design, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Guwahati. Workshop based prototype of the amphibian ambulance followed by refined field experiments and field trials were carried out at IIT Guwahati campus and Aminagon primary health centre with participatory approach. Through these trials, it was found that the vehicle was an efficient and sustainable solution compared to existing available transportation modes in this places. While the field trial were carried out, it was found the vehicle was safe for operation from the view of user friendly, comfort, easy access, protection from natural elements and also sustainable for the riverine people, which was a fully amphibian featured and which worked on land and in water.

Finally there is contextual research endeavour like design development of sustainable amphibian ambulance for riverine people in Assam to be socially responsible in the long run.

This report provides various information regarding the aim and objective of the research, human centred design methodology adopted for undertaking the design, results and analysis of the experiments carried out from the point of view of perception of the innovated and developed amphibian ambulance as a sustainable healthcare mode.

2. Introduction

India is considered as a developing country and its population is still growing. 300 million people in India still earns less than ₹ 80/- per day. Seventy per-cent of Indian population is rural and development and deployment of technologies specifically designed for this population group can improve their lifestyles and livelihoods. Most of the efforts for providing basic facility to rural areas have been based on a 'Jugad' approach, using locally available facilities, materials and expertise by the community. There are small adjustments made using low or sometimes appropriate technology.

While choosing technological intervention for this type of situation, in contrast to high-tech innovation and development, it is considered that intermediate (Schumacher, 1973) (or appropriate) technologies may be considered effective. Appropriate technology is small scale, energy efficient, low-cost, radical, environmentally sound, labor intensive, and controlled by the local rural community. As Schumacher described it:

Such an intermediate technology would be immensely more productive than the indigenous technology...but it would be immensely cheaper than the sophisticated, highly capital-intensive technology of modern industry (Schumacher, 1973).

Appropriate technology has been applied as a solution for rural development; it has also gained support as a direction for sustainable technologies. However, it has often been identified as "cheap" (or "second hand"), which is carried in modernisation by technological innovation (Vergrapt, 2005).

This research deals with health care facilities in riverine areas of Assam, locally known as *char*. In this context, in Assam, there are 2251 villages in char (riverine island) areas in which there are only 52 Primary Health Centres and 135 Sub-Centres; the numbers not sufficient to cover the entire population (www.nrhmassam.in, 10 March 2013) which is very dispersed over large geographical area. Due to problems created by flood perennially, it is difficult to construct permanent infrastructure in these areas, and people of such areas have to shift their dwellings frequently during flood time.

A pilot study was carried out in Dhakuakhana sub-division of Assam to find out shortcomings in the health services rendered to riverine areas so that possible intervention can be initiated. The key finding from this field study is split into three linked groups: the

places, the people and the problems. Information recording methods differed between locations. Observations were recorded by audio-visual medium as well as through interviews of focus groups that facilitated more accurate capture of information. This information was reflected upon and latter transcribed, without misinterpretation.

After gathering information through these field studies, the research team arrived at the conclusion that there is a potentially high demand for context specific transportation design that can lead to a better access to health care system for remote riverine areas in Assam. In addition, it can stop migration of the riverine population to urban and semi urban areas in absence of proper health care facilities in their local area.

3. Research justification

This research becomes relevant due to the possible improvement of the sustainable healthcare transportation system for riverine areas in Assam. From the pilot study, it was evident that people travel to the boat clinic by walking and also carried in whatever mode of transport is available including the bullock cart, the horse cart and the small boat if the person is immobile. The most common practice in riverine areas is that, a patient is wrapped up with clothes to be carried by a strong person to the health centres. On several occasions, patients are also found to be transported in a handcart. Even in this case, where there are small water bodies without a bridge, it becomes impossible to cross them. Therefore, patients, in many cases, never reach the health centres in time. Designing for the underprivileged section of the society is one of the basic requirements for indigenous design in Assam. This research is an attempt towards developing the current practice for meeting the local transportation needs of the poor population of remote riverine areas for accessing health centres. The solution of this type of problem can lead to a better healthcare system for the rural areas.

4. Research questions (RQ)

Research questions:

RQ1: How can products and services, in this case, an amphibian ambulance be designed in order to meet the specific needs of people living in riverine areas better way?

RQ2: How can an innovation be transferred to Non-Government organisation (NGO) as a commercialized product with the collaboration of academic institutions like IIT.

5. State of art review on improvement of healthcare transportation for riverine areas

During literature review, it has been observed that there are limited studies carried out on healthcare transportation system in the context of Assam. However, in other developing countries (African countries) people have carried out research studies on bicycle ambulance as well as motorbike ambulance.

Since this study is in the context of remote riverine areas in Assam, the literature review has been split into three categories as mentioned below:

- a) Existing health care facilities in riverine areas of Assam.
- b) Design development of ambulance based on contextual issues and relevance.
- c) Study of support for design innovation in India and western countries, Design and technology transfer point of view of design innovation, development awareness and context.

Finding from both the studies are elaborately discussed in Chapter 1 and Chapter 2 and Chapter 6 with relevant references.

6. Hypothesis (H)

H₁: If an appropriate transportation (in the context of easy to access, user friendly, comfort, safety, navigability) is designed for riverine areas in Assam, it can facilitate delivery of healthcare services.

H₂: Study of support for innovation in India and western countries may provide appropriate guidelines which will be contextual for the introduction and sustainability of the designed product.

7. Aim and objectives

Aim

The aim of this research is to design and develop appropriate transport product for providing a better healthcare access for the rural riverine area in Assam.

Objectives

- To study existing health care delivery system in the riverine areas of the Brahmaputra valley.

- To design a rural transportation system in order to meet the specific needs of people living in riverine areas based on the above study that can provide transportation both on land and in water, specifically an amphibian one.
- To study possibility of introducing innovative ambulance through NGO using participatory approach.

8. Research approach

As mentioned earlier, the aim of the research work is to develop an appropriate system for providing a better healthcare access for the rural riverine areas in the Brahmaputra valley. The research adopts the human centred design based on design thinking approach, for design and development of an appropriate technology and contextual design in health care solutions.

9. Conceptualisation and design

In the initial phase, a survey to understand the user's need was carried out. In this study, the opinions of the end users and stakeholder were considered. End users were riverine flood affected people and the stakeholder was the civil Society and NGOs. The goal of this research is to design and develop a working prototype of an amphibian ambulance by applying human centred design approaches and the morphology of design process from the concept to production. Based on the contextual study and literature study on existing health care facilities for riverine areas in Assam, the concept was initiated to provide a sustainable transportation system with amphibian characteristics. First, feasibility study was conducted in IIT Guwahati campus and different localities of the Brahmaputra valley. The second step in the feasibility study is the identification and formulation of design of amphibian ambulance.

The factors were identified and the design problem was formulated in the preliminary design of the ambulance and final design features incorporated are:

- The design consists of Catamaran type hull made of Fibre Reinforced Plastics and fitted with 3 wheels like a tricycle rickshaw to facilitate its movement on both land and water.
- The driving mechanism is foot pedalling similar to a common forms of tandem tricycle for an able-bodied user for self-travel with the stretcher placed near the rider and attendant.

- Accommodates three persons with ergonomic seating arrangement; one for the rider who controls the vehicle, another for the attendant to look after the patient and also assist in pedalling tandem tricycle mode; third one is a patient who lies on the stretcher.
- The ambulance was fabricated from bicycle, tricycle rickshaw, e- rickshaw components and steel stock, such as 25 mm round tube.
- The ambulance provided an enclosed structure for protecting the rider from the natural elements like sunlight, and rain.
- Provided proper space for attendant to carry first-aid equipment.
- Provided ground clearance of 200 mm from the ground level to the chassis level.
- For the comfort of the patient, the angle of the stretcher was maintained at around 10 degrees, which is ergonomically optimum angle for sleeping purpose. The size of stretcher is 1800 mm × 610 mm.
- The tare weight of the amphibian ambulance is 225 Kg. (without passengers) and the spring balance reading for dragging it with three people is 17 Kg. from the rest.
- The vehicle has an aesthetically appealing form, with a contemporary visual identity in the Indian context.
- The amphibian ambulance has been branded as 'Dola'; conceptually the Dola is known as a Palki or palanquin. The term has derived its name from the Sanskrit word 'Palanki' meaning a bed or couch, suspended by the four corners from a bamboo pole. The Palki used to be carried by two bearers. Palki has two doors openings on both sides. The image in **Figure 1** symbolises the Palki.

Figure 1: A man being carried on a palanquin by Indian bearers
(etc.usf.edu/clipart/49800/49807/49807_palanquin.htm, 21 March 2016)

Once the design and development was completed, it was prototyped. The newly designed amphibian ambulance was found to be functionally satisfactory while tested on land and in water. Image of the prototyped vehicle is shown in **Figure 2**.

In addition, the ambulance may be recommended for travel to a distance less than 3 Km (in which case it will cover most of the target area). During trial, it has been used for distance of up to 6 Km. The amphibian ambulance can travel at an approximate speed of 9 Km/h on road and 3 Km/h in water. It also accommodates patients with a diversity of conditions, including cholera, malaria, obstetrics, and orthopaedics.

Figure 2 (a): Designed and developed amphibian ambulance on land

Figure 2 (b): Designed and developed amphibian ambulance in water

Figure 2: Prototype of designed and developed amphibian ambulance

10. Product test programme, data collection and analysis

To assess acceptance of the amphibian ambulance by the user, for its performance and efficiency, it was required to be evaluated through actual field trials. For the design evaluation of the amphibian ambulance, seven experimental tests were formulated and these were carried out by 27 users at IIT Guwahati campus and Amingaon primary health centre, Kamrup.

Objectives of these tests were to assess the followings:

- i. Users perception regarding ease of use of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance to drive while driving on land and in water by two persons pedalling simultaneously and compare.
- ii. Users perception regarding the newly designed amphibian ambulance in terms of user- friendliness and compatibility while driving on land and in water by two people and compare.
- iii. Users perception regarding the comfort issue of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance while riding on land and in water by the rider and compare.
- iv. Users perception regarding the comfort issue of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance while riding on land and in water by the attendant and compare.
- v. Users perception regarding the feeling of safety of the amphibian ambulance while riding on land and in water by the rider and the attendant and compare.
- vi. Users perception regarding the ease of use (entry/exit) of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance while the vehicle is on land and in water by the rider and the attendant and compare.
- vii. Users perception regarding the front visibility of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance while riding on land and in water by the rider.
- viii. Users perception regarding the protection from the natural elements issue of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance while driving on land and in water by the rider and the attendant and compare.
- ix. Users perception regarding the effect of navigation of the amphibian ambulance while driving on land and in water and compare.
- x. Users perception regarding the space requirement of patient to lie on the stretcher while operating the amphibian ambulance on land and in water.
- xi. Users perception regarding the visual appearance of the vehicle as an ambulance while operate on land.

- xii. People perception regarding the visual image of the vehicle as an amphibian ambulance while operating on land and in water.

10.1 Findings from the experiments

Findings and interpretations of the above experiments are provided in sections 10.2 to 10.13.

10.2 Experiment no. 1: Users perception regarding ease of use of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance to drive while driving on land and in water by two persons pedalling simultaneously and compare.

Findings and interpretation of paired sample t-test for experiment no. 1.

Comparison of two different contexts using the newly designed amphibian ambulance in perceiving the *easy to drive* issue or factor while driving on land and in water by two persons pedalling simultaneously.

Table 1: Paired Samples Statistics for experiment no. 1

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	The vehicle is easy to drive with two persons pedalling simultaneously on land	3.33	27	1.038	.200
	The vehicle is easy to drive with two persons pedalling simultaneously in water	3.56	27	.934	.180

Table 2: Paired Samples Correlations for experiment no. 1

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	The vehicle is easy to drive with two persons pedalling simultaneously on land & The vehicle is easy to drive with two persons pedalling simultaneously in water	27	.556	.003

Table 3: Paired Sample test for experiment no. 1

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	The vehicle is easy to drive with two human pedalling simultaneously on land – The vehicle is easy to drive with two human pedalling simultaneously in water	-.222	.934	.180	-.592	.147	-1.237	26	.227

Interpretation of experiment no. 1

H₀₁- Null hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the rider’s perception in the context of ‘ease of drive’ with two persons pedalling simultaneously on land and in water.

A Paired sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (Two- tailed sig.: 0.227 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference of ease of drive with two human pedalling simultaneously on land and in water.

10.3 Experiment no. 2: Users perception regarding the newly designed amphibian ambulance in terms of user- friendliness and compatibility while driving on land and in water by two people and compare.

Findings and interpretation of paired sample t-test for experiment no. 2.

Comparison of two different contexts using the newly designed amphibian ambulance in perceiving the *user friendly and compatibility factor* while driving on land and in water by two people.

Table 4: Paired Samples Statistics for experiment no. 2

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Design is user- friendly and compatible for use by two people on land	3.44	27	.698	.134
	Design is user- friendly and compatible for use by two people in water	3.70	27	.953	.183

Table 5: Paired Samples Correlations for experiment no. 2

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Design is user- friendly and compatible for use by two people on land & Design is user friendly and compatible for use by two people in water	27	.437	.023

Table 6: Paired Samples Test for experiment no. 2

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Design is user friendly and compatible for use by two people on land - Design is user friendly and compatible for use by two people in water	-.259	.903	.174	-.616	.098	-1.492	26	.148

Interpretation of experiment no. 2

H₀₂- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the riders' perception in the context of user friendly and compatibility for use by two people while driving on land and in water.

A Paired sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (Two- tailed sig.: 0.148 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference in the vehicle in its user friendly and compatibility for use by two people on land and in water.

10.4 Experiment no. 3: Users perception regarding the comfort issue of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance while riding on land and in water by the rider and compare.

Findings and interpretation of paired sample t-test for experiment no. 3.

Comparison of two different contexts using the newly designed amphibian ambulance in perceiving the *comfort* while riding on land and in water by the rider.

Table 7: Paired Samples Statistics for experiment no. 3

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Comfort to ride the ambulance on land	3.37	27	1.043	.201
	Comfort to ride the ambulance in water	3.59	27	1.083	.209

Table 8: Paired Samples Correlations for experiment no. 3

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Comfort to ride the ambulance on land & Comfort to ride the ambulance in water	27	.615	.001

Table 9: Paired Samples Test for experiment no. 3

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Comfort to ride the ambulance on land - Comfort to ride the ambulance in water	-.222	.934	.180	-.592	.147	-1.237	26	.227

Interpretation of experiment no. 3

H₀₃- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the riders' perception in the context of riders' comfort while riding the ambulance on land and in water.

A Paired sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (Two- tailed sig.: 0.227 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference of riders' comfort while the ambulance is on land and in water.

10.5 Experiment no. 4: Users perception regarding the comfort issue of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance while riding on land and in water by the attendant and compare.

Findings and interpretation of paired sample t-test for experiment no. 4.

Comparison of two different contexts using the newly designed amphibian ambulance in perceiving the *comfort* while riding on land and in water by the attendant

Table 10: Paired Samples Statistics for experiment no. 4

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Attendant's comfort to ride the ambulance on land	3.48	27	.893	.172
	Attendant's comfort to ride the ambulance in water	3.74	27	.764	.147

Table 11: Paired Samples Correlations for experiment no. 4

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Attendant's comfort to ride the ambulance on land & attendant's comfort to ride the ambulance in water	27	.472	.013

Table 12: Paired Samples Test for experiment no. 4

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Attendant's comfort to ride the ambulance on land - Attendant's comfort to ride the ambulance in water	-.259	.859	.165	-.599	.081	-1.568	26	.129

Interpretation of experiment no. 4

H04- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the attendant’s perception in the context of his/her comfort while riding the ambulance on land and in water.

A Paired sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (Two- tailed sig.: 0.129 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference of attendant’s comfort while riding the ambulance on land and in water.

10.6 Experiment no. 5: Users perception regarding the feeling of safety of the amphibian ambulance while riding on land and in water by the rider and the attendant and compare.

Findings and interpretation of paired sample t-test for experiment no. 5.

Comparison of two different contexts using the newly designed amphibian ambulance in perceiving the *feeling of safety* while riding on land and in water by the rider and attendant.

Table 13: Paired Samples Statistics for experiment no. 5

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Feeling of safety in the ambulance while driving on land	3.56	27	1.121	.216
	Feeling of safety in the ambulance while driving in water	3.63	27	.926	.178

Table 14: Paired Samples Correlations for experiment no. 5

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Feeling of safety in the ambulance while driving on land & Feeling of safety in the ambulance while driving in water	27	.465	.014

Table 15: Paired Samples Test for experiment no. 5

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Feeling of safety in the ambulance while driving on land - Feeling of safety in the ambulance while driving in water	-.074	1.072	.206	-.498	.350	-.359	26	.722

Interpretation of experiment no. 5

H₀₅. Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the riders' perception in the context of safety in the ambulance is on land and in water.

A Paired sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (Two- tailed sig.: 0.722 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference of rider's safety while riding the ambulance on land and in water.

10.7 Experiment no. 6: Users perception regarding the ease of use (entry/exit) of the newly- designed amphibian ambulance while the vehicle is on land and in water by the rider and the attendant and compare.

Findings and interpretation of paired sample t-test for experiment no. 6.

Comparison of two different contexts using the newly designed amphibian ambulance in perceiving the *easy to access factor* (entry/exit) by the rider and the attendant while the vehicle is on land and in water.

Table 16: Paired Samples Statistics for experiment no. 6

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	The vehicle is easy to access (entry/exit) on land	4.00	27	.734	.141
	The vehicle is easy to access (entry/exit) in water	4.00	27	.620	.119

Table 17: Paired Samples Correlations for experiment no. 6

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	The vehicle is easy to access (entry/exit) on land & The vehicle is easy to access (entry/exit) in water	27	.423	.028

Table 18: Paired Samples Test for experiment no. 6

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	The vehicle is easy to access (entry/exit) on land – The vehicle is easy to access (entry/exit) in water	.000	.734	.141	-.290	.290	.000	26	1.000

Interpretation of experiment no. 6

H₀₆- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the riders' perception on land and in water in the context of 'ease of access' to the ambulance.

A Paired sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (Two- tailed sig.: $1.0 > 0.05$) and concluded that there is no significant difference of ease of access to the ambulance is on land and in water.

10.8 Experiment no. 7: Users perception regarding the front visibility of the newly designed amphibian ambulance while riding on land and in water by the rider.

Findings and interpretation of paired sample t-test for experiment no. 7.

Comparison of two different contexts using the newly designed amphibian ambulance in perceiving the *front visibility* while riding on land and in water by the rider.

Table 19: Paired Samples Statistics for experiment no. 7

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Front visibility during driving on land	4.07	27	.874	.168
	Front visibility during driving in water	4.04	27	.854	.164

Table 20: Paired Samples Correlations for experiment no. 7

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Front visibility during driving on land & Front visibility during driving in water	27	.975	.000

Table 21: Paired Samples Test for experiment no. 7

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Front visibility during driving on land – Front visibility during driving in water	.037	.192	.037	-.039	.113	1.000	26	.327

Interpretation of experiment no. 7

H₀₇- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the riders' perception in the context of front visibility of the rider during driving the ambulance on land and in water.

A Paired sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (Two- tailed sig.: 0.327 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference in terms of front visibility of the rider during driving the ambulance is on land and in water.

10.9 Experiment no. 8: Users perception regarding the protection from the natural elements of the newly designed amphibian ambulance while driving on land and in water by the rider and the attendant and compare.

Findings and interpretation of paired sample t-test for experiment no. 8.

Comparison of two different contexts using the newly designed amphibian ambulance in perceiving the *protection from the natural elements* factor while driving on land and in water by the rider and the attendant.

Table 22: Paired Samples Statistics for experiment no. 8

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Protection from the elements of weather on land	4.00	27	1.000	.192
	Protection from the elements of weather in water	4.22	27	.974	.187

Table 23: Paired Samples Correlations for experiment no. 8

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Protection from the elements of weather on land & Protection from the elements of weather in water	27	.592	.001

Table 24: Paired Samples Test for experiment no. 8

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Protection from the elements of weather on land - Protection from the elements of weather in water	-.222	.892	.172	-.575	.130	-1.295	26	.207

Interpretation of experiment no. 8

H₀₈- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the riders' perception in the context of protection from the weather while driving the ambulance on land and in water.

A Paired sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (Two- tailed sig.: 0.207 > 0.05) and it is concluded that there is no significant difference for weather protection of the ambulance on land and in water.

10.10 Experiment no. 9: Users perception regarding the effect of navigation of the amphibian ambulance while driving on land and in water and compare.

Findings and interpretation of paired sample t-test for experiment no. 9.

Comparison of effect of navigation of amphibian ambulance while driving on land and in water.

Table 25: Paired Samples Statistics for experiment no. 9

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Navigability on land	3.81	27	1.001	.193
	Navigability in water in water	4.04	27	1.091	.210

Table 26: Paired Samples Correlations for experiment no. 9

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Navigability on land & Navigability in water in water	27	.499	.008

Table 27: Paired Samples Test for experiment no. 9

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Navigability on land - Navigability in water in water	-.222	1.050	.202	-.638	.193	-1.100	26	.282

Interpretation of experiment no. 9

H₀₉- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference the riders' perception on land and in water in the context of navigation.

A Paired sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (Two- tailed sig.: 0.282 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference of navigability of the ambulance while driving on land and in water.

10.11 Experiment no. 10: Users perception regarding the space requirement of patient to lie on the stretcher while operating the amphibian ambulance on land and in water.

Findings and interpretation of One-way ANOVA test for experiment no. 10.

Comparison of space requirement of stretcher regarding patient comfort of the amphibian ambulance in the context of gender (male and female).

Table 28: Descriptive statistics of rating on level for experiment no. 10

The patient's comfort								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min	Max
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Male	24	3.71	.955	.195	3.31	4.11	2	5
Female	3	4.00	1.000	.577	1.52	6.48	3	5
Total	27	3.74	.944	.182	3.37	4.11	2	5

Table 29: One-way ANOVA test for experiment no. 10

The patient's comfort					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	.227	1	.227	.247	.624
Within Groups	22.958	25	.918		
Total	23.185	26			

Interpretation of experiment no. 10

H₁₀- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the patients' perception on land and in water in the context of gender.

A dependent sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (sig.: 0.624 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference of gender and patient's perception on *patient's comfort* while lying on the stretcher of the vehicle on land and in water.

10.12 Experiment no. 11: Users perception regarding the visual appearance of the vehicle as an ambulance while operating on land.

Findings and interpretation of One-way ANOVA test for experiment no. 11.

Comparison of visual appearance of the vehicle as an ambulance while operating on land in the context of gender.

Table 30: Descriptive statistics of rating on level for experiment no. 11

Visual appearance of the ambulance while driving on land								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Male	24	4.29	.859	.175	3.93	4.65	2	5
Female	3	4.67	.577	.333	3.23	6.10	4	5
Total	27	4.33	.832	.160	4.00	4.66	2	5

Table 31: One-way ANOVA test for experiment no. 11

Visual appearance of the ambulance while driving on land					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	.375	1	.375	.532	.473
Within Groups	17.625	25	.705		
Total	18.000	26			

Interpretation of experiment no. 11

H₁₁- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the public perception of visual appearance of the vehicle as an ambulance on land in the context of gender.

A dependent sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (sig.: 0.473 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference of gender and public perception of *visual appearance* of the vehicle as an ambulance while on land.

10.13 Experiment no. 12: People perception regarding the visual image of the vehicle as an amphibian ambulance while operating on land and in water.

Findings and interpretation of One-way ANOVA test for experiment no. 12.

Comparison of visual appearance of the vehicle as an amphibian ambulance while operating in water in the context of gender.

Table 32: Descriptive statistics of rating on level for experiment no. 12

Visual appearance of the ambulance while sailing in water								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min	Max
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Male	24	4.25	.794	.162	3.91	4.59	2	5
Female	3	4.33	.577	.333	2.90	5.77	4	5
Total	27	4.26	.764	.147	3.96	4.56	2	5

Table 33: One-way ANOVA test for experiment no. 12

Visual appearance of the ambulance while sailing in water					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	.019	1	.019	.031	.863
Within Groups	15.167	25	.607		
Total	15.185	26			

Interpretation of experiment no. 12

H₁₂- Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the public perception of visual appearance in water in the context of gender.

A dependent sample detail has been conducted for a significant level of 0.05.

The null hypothesis is accepted (sig.: 0.863 > 0.05) and concluded that there is no significant difference of gender and public perception on *visual appearance* of the vehicle as an amphibian ambulance while operating on land and in water.

11. Institutionalisation of innovation

Once the design of the amphibian ambulance was found to be acceptable, next challenge was to find out way to introduce the same in the target area. Since the research work was without any financial support for its introduction in the contextual area. The study was done to find out appropriate way to achieve the same.

Though product innovation is one of the key strategic options available to SMEs in developing economies in order to compete better in today's global market, the contextual factors that affect the product's acceptance in the market was investigated. In this regard, it has investigated the factors that affect indigenous innovation during the Erasmus Mundus Interweave fellowship programme at Cardiff Metropolitan University, Wales for commercialisation of the newly designed amphibian ambulance. The design support for indigenous innovations at grassroots level is provided by the National Innovation Foundation (NIF), India. However, NIF does not provide financial support to science and technology background researchers. It provides financial support only to innovators who do not come from engineering background. But, in Wales, the Welsh Government provides support for all local innovators and also their ideas in the initial stage for the implementation of the final product including business innovation to drive business success. NIF and Government of India should come out with a mechanism to provide funding support from already established Government funded agencies like the District Industries & Commerce Centres (DICCC), the Prototype Development and Training Centre (NSIC), New Delhi, and the Centre for Entrepreneurship Development (CED) for development of the newly designed amphibian ambulance. National Health Mission can adopt this context specific design innovation and should provide this facility to the riverine areas in the Brahmaputra valley.

Inhabitants of the riverine areas should be encouraged to support and accept this type of health care solutions. The acceptance by the community is essential for the success of amphibian ambulance.

12. Validation of the hypotheses

The first hypothesis formulated is "If an appropriate transportation (in the context of easy to access, user friendly, comfort, safety, navigability and general appearance) is designed for riverine areas in Assam, it can facilitate delivery of healthcare services." It has been fully established after conducting a number of exhaustive experiments

numbering twelve in different phases, as described in Experiment no. 1 (section 10.2), Experiment no. 2 (section 10.3), Experiment no. 3 (section 10.4), Experiment no. 4 (section 10.5), Experiment no. 5 (section 10.6), Experiment no. 6 (section 10.7), Experiment no. 7 (section 10.8), Experiment no. 8 (section 10.9), Experiment no. 9 (section 10.10), Experiment no. 10 (section 10.11), Experiment no. 11 (section 10.12), Experiment no. 12 (section 10.13). The interpretation of results of various experiments as mentioned is also given. Findings from above interpretations of (Experiment no. 1 to Experiment no. 9) clearly indicate that the newly designed vehicle is perceived as an amphibian vehicle. It was also found to be user- friendly, compatible and easy to drive by two people while running on land and in water. From the interpretation of Experiment no. 10, it has been found that the stretcher of amphibian ambulance is comfortable to lie while the vehicle operates in both situations. It has also been found that the visual appearance of the vehicle is appropriate as an amphibian ambulance while running on land and in water.

The second hypothesis formulated is that ‘Study of support for innovation in India and Western country like Wales, UK has provided an appropriate guideline which is contextual.’ It has been fully established after conducting a study covering design support for grassroots innovation in both countries.

Findings from the study shows that the innovations in India should also be fostered through eight creative ways as given below and that will be a guideline to fulfil the challenge for successful commercialisation of the amphibian ambulance for the people of low-income groups.

- Encourage the growth of micro-venture finance.
- Expand the public pool of innovations by providing financial incentives to innovators.
- Recognise, respect, and reward innovators where they live.
- Create community fabrication workshops in the homes of innovators.
- Build partnerships between formal and informal science.
- Mobilise university students to address unsolved social problems.
- Promote local innovation for environment- suited farming and asset management.
- Collaborate between formal and informal sector economy (formal sector- high income groups and informal sector- low income groups).

13. Contribution of the present research

The research has contributed to the knowledge in the area of contextual design and possible design and technology transfer of the amphibian ambulance to the potential market in Indian context, specifically considering the rural riverine areas in Assam.

The outcome of the research provides a solution to improve the current transportation system in remote riverine areas in Assam for accessing health care services. As mentioned earlier, context specific design and development of an innovative product is the best possible way to solve the problem of accessibility to health care services in rural riverine areas where proper road network does not exist. The newly designed and developed amphibian ambulance branded as *Dola* was prototyped and its manufacturing system management was evolved in the Department of Design, IIT Guwahati with participation from M/s Dipon Design Pvt. Ltd., a start-up under Technology Incubation Centre under IIT Guwahati located at North Guwahati, Kamrup, Assam.

Given fact that emergency service care can make an important contribution to reducing avoidable death and disability in low-income groups in developing countries, the designed and developed amphibian ambulance can play a very significant role. With better planning and co-ordination with boat clinics etc., within the present cost incurred for emergency care at present can achieve higher outcomes. This type of research can lead to filling up the gaps in accessing health care facilities in target areas including emergency care.

14. Suggestions and recommendation

The following are the suggestions for consideration while adopting and using the newly designed amphibian ambulance as a sustainable transportation mode:

- Rider should be a male person who can control the vehicle and attendant may be either a male or a female.
- For the ease of use while transporting patients to and from health care facilities require crossing water bodies without bridges, the banks of these water bodies can be prepared by cutting it at a slope so that getting the amphibian ambulance into the water and getting it out of the water is easy. Wooden poles can be fixed at the banks where the wire ropes of the winch fitted in the ambulance can be tied and winched to get it in or out of the water very smoothly with less effort.
- The winch fixed at the rear end of the amphibian ambulance should be used to get it out of a situation such as when the vehicle gets stuck in the muddy water.

- A gasoline fuel engine or electric motor can be coupled with the transmission system of the ambulance to propel it by a propeller at the time of water mode operation.
- Propeller should be possible to be disengaged while the vehicle is used only on land.

15. Limitation of the current research

The research is based on a specific context and hypothesis. Thus, the vehicle is suitable for flash flood water or a small pond.

Since number of participants for the experiments was less, the validity of the designed experiments depends on the feedback of the participants and may vary with larger nos. of participants and this is one limitation of the research. This part may be undertaken as future research.

15.1 Future scope

There are possibilities for further development of the design in different variation such as public transportation, as a means of recreational amphibian tricycle throughout India.

Another area for further research is regarding the conversion of this amphibian ambulance to an electric powered one using photovoltaic solar panels for charging the storage battery and then propelling the ambulance through electric motor.

In addition, the designed amphibian ambulance can be used in semi urban and urban areas at the time of flash flood. This has been the opinion of the people from Guwahati city who have seen this product in IIT Guwahati and they have found it to be justified. Guwahati city regularly gets flooded in monsoon due to flash flood.

15.2 Contextual design and appropriate technology transfer

For the contextual design and appropriate technology transfer for making the amphibian ambulance available in the target areas, different agencies, local NGOs, and local SMEs has been approached. Thus, there is a scope for future work for commercialisation in the target areas that can be explored.

16. The outline of the thesis framework

The thesis is structured into the following chapters.

Chapter 1 titled ‘Introduction: Health Care Facilities in Riverine Areas of Assam’. The introduction deals with rural health care facilities available in the context of the study, i.e. riverine areas in the Brahmaputra valley. It also deals with the Aim and Objectives of the research.

Chapter 2 titled ‘Design Development of the Ambulance: Issues and Contextual Relevance’, contains discussion regarding traditional transportation system in rural India as well as the existing intermediate ambulance in global situation. Briefly describes the history of different types of bicycle, tricycle, tandem cycle with structural layout. The chapter covers status and associated factors relevant to the Indian cultural context.

Chapter 3 titled ‘Conceptual Design of an Amphibian Ambulance’ covers design and development brief for amphibian ambulance, feasibility study, identification and formulation of the design problem, different concepts and evaluation. Also it deals with preliminary design with testing of mathematical model and validation of the design concept.

Chapter 4 titled ‘Detailed Design, Prototyping and Testing of the Amphibian Ambulance’, describes the detailed design process for selected concept of the newly designed and developed amphibian ambulance. Also it covers various prototyping phases and field trials on land and in water and redesigning of the parts based on user feedbacks.

Chapter 5 titled ‘Product Test Programme, Data Collection and Analysis’, covers experimental set up and preparation of questionnaires. Describes operational testing of the prototype through actual field trial on land and in water and also describes validation of the design and research hypothesis through the results of field trials. Statistical analysis of data collected in the experiments and discussion on the field experiments and the methodology adopted are described in details.

Chapter 6 titled ‘Institutionalisation of innovation’, covers contextual guidelines for support to innovators between two countries viz. India and Wales and compares and contrasts how grassroots innovations are supported in a developing country such as India with how the support is offered in Wales, UK.

Chapter 7 titled ‘Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendation’, describes the finding of the research, contribution and limitations of the current research. Describes the future scopes of work for the development of the concept and its greater application. Also mentions recommendation for the application of the finding of the research in the remote riverine areas in the Brahmaputra valley.

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